

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable 3.12

Report on integrated biomedical data and project proposals for biomarker validation in clinical trial monitoring

WP3 – Community Driven Cross-Infrastructure joint research – Medical

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Executive Summary

The work package aimed to integrate the resources in four (later five) different biobanks in four countries to find early (preclinical) biomarkers for pancreatic cancer, a currently rapidly lethal cancer for which no treatment is available, most likely due largely to the late and advanced stage in which it is diagnosed. First this was attempted with metabolomics, through which two biomarkers of potential interest were found, glutamine and histidine, these were of too low impact to have clinical utility, despite findings of biological interest. Then the attention was turned to proteomics and here 6 proteins of oncological relevance were found as potential biomarkers: GZMH, VEGFR2, FGF1P, GPNMB, CRTAC1 and ITGAV. As the next step, their clinical interest is being independently validated followed by integrated multi-omics analysis.

Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached/this deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) integrate four national prospective cohorts in sample provision and generation and -analysis to discover early disease biomarkers
- b) assess and report on the utility of metabolic biomarkers for pancreatic cancer
- c) assess the utility of proteomic biomarkers for pancreatic cancer (report pending validation)

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background

SubWP 3.5 aims to join four prospective cohorts in Estonia, Finland, Norway and the Netherlands, in a transnational effort to discover early biomarkers for pancreatic cancer. While this disease is rapidly fatal, no predictive or preclinical biomarkers exist, greatly reducing therapeutic options. The previous deliverable D3.11 reported on subtask 3.5.1 *Collating and expanding the consortium*, and 3.5.2 on *Sample selection and verification*. This deliverable, D3.12, reports on subtasks 3.5.3 *Data generation and analysis*, and 3.5.4 *Dissemination*. It is the central part of the study: the identification and validation of putative predictive biomarkers for pancreas cancer.

Description of Work

Subtask 3.5.3. Data generation and analysis.

After quality assessment we retained 356 cases and 887 controls. In the data harmonization, the HUNT biobank (Norway) material was analysed as two sections, HUNT2 and HUNT3 due to different characteristics, bringing the no. of biobanks up to 5. 1H-NMR Metabolomics data were generated on the Nightingale platform (Vantaa, Finland). Several statistical analyses were performed, including logistic regression on the complete dataset and the individual cohorts; meta-analysis of the individual cohorts and LASSO-penalized logistic regression. We identified two significant hits: glutamine ($p=0.011$) and histidine ($p=0.012$), However, both had high adjusted p-values (0.42 each). Lasso analysis showed a slight improvement of the ROC curves when including gln and his, but too little for

clinical utility. Biologically noteworthy observations are that differences between cases and controls are greater in diabetics than non-diabetics, and that stratification of onset in 0-2, 2-5, and 5-10+ years after sampling, shows a difference in glutamine only for onset after 2-5 and 5-10+ years but no longer for onset within 2 years, while for histidine the difference is greatest for onset in 0-2 years, smaller for 2-5 years and absent for 5-10+ years. This would suggest glutamine being involved in an earlier process, tapering out closer to onset, and histidine in a process closer to the actual onset. We identified two significant hits: *glutamine* ($p=0.011$) and *histidine* ($p=0.012$), but with high adjusted p -values of 0.42 each. Prognostic strength improved slightly when including *gln* and *his*, but too little for clinical utility. Two biologically noteworthy observations are (i) differences between cases and controls are greater in diabetics than non-diabetics, and (ii) stratification of onset suggests glutamine being involved in an earlier process, and histidine in a process closer to the actual onset. Our results imply that, while identifying *gln* and *his* as early biomarkers of potential biological interest, a study at this scale does not yield metabolomic biomarkers with sufficient predictive value to be clinically useful *per se* for integrated use as prognostic biomarkers. In the light of this, validation was put on hold and the study expanded to 180 proteomics biomarkers of potential oncological and metabolic relevance, using the Olink proteomics platform, run by FUGU at THL (Helsinki, Finland) to achieve a next level of biomedical data integration. Despite use of a more limited sample set out of cost considerations, (74 cases with onset <2y and 108 controls), indeed six protein biomarkers of oncological interest are identified: *GZMH*, *VEGFR2*, *FGFBP1*, *GPNMB*, *CRTAC1* and *ITGAV*.

Subtask 3.5.4. Dissemination.

The metabolomics part of the study has been published by *Endocrinology*¹ and has been placed on the bioRxiv preprint server for global accessibility². The proteomics results and integrated multi-omics analysis will be submitted after validation.

Next steps

The proteomics biomarkers will now be validated by a more focused, but similar analysis, at SciLifeLab (Uppsala, Sweden), followed by assessment of their predictive value in integrated biomedical data analysis.

Publications

Search for early pancreatic cancer blood biomarkers in five European prospective population biobanks using metabolomics. Jesse Fest, Lisanne S Vijfhuizen, Jelle J Goeman, Olga Veth, Anni Joensuu, Markus Perola, Satu Mannist, Eivind Ness-Jensen, Kristian Hveem, Toomas Haller, Neeme Tonisson, Kairit Mikkel, Andres Metspalu, Cornelia M van Duijn, Arfan Ikram, Bruno H Stricker, Rikje Ruiter, Casper HJ van Eijck, Gertjan B van Ommen, Peter AC 't Hoen
doi: 10.1210/en.2019-00165^{3,4}

¹<https://academic.oup.com/endo/advance-article/doi/10.1210/en.2019-00165/5497119?guestAccessKey=10ab457c-b241-4584-ba99-6b492c7b7745>

² <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/543686v1>

³ <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2019-00165>

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is largely on time and to a small part delayed as the proteomics results, while obtained, still need to be validated, followed by a final integrated analysis. This can be achieved within budget and within the extension time of the CORBEL projects.

Adjustments made

Following the low clinical utility of the metabolomics biomarkers per se, the data generation was successfully extended to include proteomics analysis.

Appendices

N/A

⁴<https://academic.oup.com/endo/advance-article/doi/10.1210/en.2019-00165/5497119?guestAccessKey=10ab457c-b241-4584-ba99-6b492c7b7745>